

Bibliometric Trends and Patterns in the Academic Approach to Interdisciplinary Topics

K. N. Ramos G.*

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1 Abstract

This study addresses the growing need for interdisciplinary research to solve complex problems in academic contexts. The goal was to analyze term and discipline co-occurrences in 10,000 articles using co-occurrence matrices that categorize different knowledge areas and popular terms. The methodology included constructing these matrices, summing rows to estimate the influence of each discipline, and applying a community detection algorithm to identify clusters of related terms. The results revealed that disciplines such as Biochemistry, Management, and Agriculture exhibit high co-occurrence, indicating their relevance in interdisciplinary dialogue. The detected communities showed two main emphases: one focused on social and managerial aspects, and another centered on data analysis and scientific methodologies. It was observed that less-represented disciplines, such as Health and Biology, have significant opportunities to integrate their approaches with more active areas. The study suggests that fostering collaborations across disciplines can enrich research and facilitate innovative solutions. Such integration is essential to address contemporary challenges and advance knowledge effectively.

1.1 Keywords

Interdisciplinarity, Co-occurrence, Collaboration, Methods, Influence

2 Introduction

Network analysis has become a fundamental tool in interdisciplinary research, enabling a deeper understanding of the complexity inherent in interactions among different fields of knowledge. In a global context characterized by increasingly complex social and scientific challenges, interdisciplinarity becomes an indispensable approach for addressing problems that cannot be fully

understood or solved from a single disciplinary perspective.

This study aims to examine trends and patterns in the academic literature on interdisciplinarity, focusing on scientific collaboration networks. Following the perspective presented by Barabási, it is argued that the structure and dynamics of these networks not only reflect interactions among researchers, but also influence knowledge diffusion and innovation. By mapping connections between disciplines and analyzing how these networks evolve, the study seeks to identify emerging areas of collaboration and highlight the most effective methodologies for fostering genuinely interdisciplinary research. [1]

A growing area of interest is that of knowledge graphs, defined as structures that represent concepts and the relationships among them in a semantic way. In the context of data science, these graphs are powerful tools that enable researchers to model and analyze complex information more effectively. [2] [3] note that knowledge graphs facilitate the integration of dispersed information and allow researchers to discover patterns and relationships that might otherwise go unnoticed if examined in isolation. This approach is especially crucial in interdisciplinary research, where connecting diverse knowledge areas can generate new perspectives and innovative solutions to complex problems.

Historical Developments in Interdisciplinary Research The development of interdisciplinary research has been an evolutionary process that has gained importance since the mid-twentieth century. One of the most relevant milestones in this context was the 1963 report of the United States Research and Development Commission, which advocated a more collaborative approach to scientific research, emphasizing the need to cross disciplinary boundaries [4].

Since then, there has been a significant increase in the publication of articles spanning multiple disciplines. This growth has been driven by the increasing complexity of social and scientific problems, such as climate change, public health, and technological innovation, which require integrated and collaborative approaches [5]. In this sense, building collaboration net-

*kramosg@unal.edu.co

works among researchers from different disciplines has become a fundamental mechanism for fostering creativity and innovation in science.

Despite the rise in interdisciplinary research output, there remains a gap in understanding how these collaboration networks are structured and how they evolve. This study seeks to address this gap through a bibliometric analysis of academic literature, identifying trends, recurring concepts, and methodologies in interdisciplinary research. The justification for this work lies in the need to better understand the dynamics of scientific collaboration networks and their impact on the advancement of knowledge.

Moreover, by investigating relationships among disciplines, this work contributes to identifying less-explored areas that could benefit from greater interdisciplinary integration. Ultimately, the aim is to provide a solid basis for future research that seeks to foster collaboration across fields, promoting a more holistic approach to solving complex problems.

3 Objective

The objective of this project was to analyze trends and patterns in the academic approach to interdisciplinary topics [6]. This included identifying recurring concepts, methodologies, and approaches in the scientific literature over time. The study also sought to determine how collaboration networks between disciplines have been structured and which approaches have been used most frequently. This bibliometric analysis was carried out in order to generate a more accurate understanding of the evolution of interdisciplinary work [7] and its representation in the scientific literature.

4 Methodology

The methodology consisted of several stages, beginning with the collection of scientific articles and followed by a detailed analysis of their texts. The steps were as follows:

4.1 Data collection

The **Scopus** database was used to search for and download scientific articles. Searches were performed using combinations of the following keywords:

- (Networks OR Network OR Networking)
- Interdisciplinary

- (Collaboration OR Collaborations)
- Science
- Review
- Knowledge

These keywords were connected using the logical operator **AND** to ensure that all retrieved articles included these words explicitly in their titles or abstracts. As a result, a total of **62,104** articles were identified in the **Scopus** database. Given the publication volume, the **10,000** most-cited articles were selected in order to perform a more focused analysis.

Additionally, using options available in the database interface, it was possible to extract the number of articles associated with different disciplines.

4.2 Text processing

Subsequently, the titles and abstracts of the selected articles were downloaded. These texts were combined and processed using text mining techniques implemented in **Python**. In this phase, the following libraries were used:

- **NLTK** (Natural Language Toolkit) for tokenization and text cleaning.
- **re** (regular expressions) to remove special characters and non-alphanumeric symbols.
- **matplotlib** to visualize results in the form of plots.
- **collections.Counter** to count word frequencies.

pandas was used for data handling and manipulation. Titles and abstracts were combined into a single column called **Combined**. The texts were tokenized, symbols removed, and stopwords filtered using **NLTK**. Text cleaning included removing symbols such as "(", ")", ".", ",", and special characters such as "(c)" or "©", in order to process only relevant words.

4.3 Frequency and co-occurrence extraction

To identify relationships among the most frequent words, the 25 most common words from the processed corpus were extracted. This analysis made it possible to identify the most recurrent terms in interdisciplinary academic studies, providing an overview of predominant concepts. A co-occurrence matrix was then built for

these 25 words, where each entry represented the number of articles in which two specific words appeared together in the title or abstract.

The co-occurrence matrix was computed using a set-based approach. For each article, sets of tokenized and filtered words were created, and the presence of two words in the same article was evaluated. The resulting matrix was visualized via a heatmap using matplotlib, enabling a visual inspection of the most common relationships among selected words.

5 Results

The analysis of the **10,000** most-cited articles in the **Scopus** database revealed consistent usage patterns in certain keywords (1). The most frequent terms, such as "research", "social", "knowledge", "study", "data", "learning", and "analysis", indicated sustained interest in research on scientific collaboration networks and interdisciplinary work. Based on these words, it is possible to compare with Zipf's law, which establishes a pattern in the distribution of words in human languages. Although in our case Zipf's law is not followed due to the removal of stopwords, it helps us infer that the inverse power-law exponent is greater than one, compared with the exponent equal to one that is typical of Zipf's law (2).

Figure 1: Most frequent words across 10,000 articles using the specified searches.

Figure 2: Zipf's law for words in the texts without considering stopwords.

It was also found that the three disciplines with the greatest influence under this set of search terms are Social Sciences, Computer Science, and Business, in this order (3). Future work will analyze these results further in order to relate disciplines to each other via co-occurrences.

Figure 3: Number of articles by discipline.

The co-occurrence matrix showed that certain terms tend to appear together in articles, suggesting that many of the studies reviewed share similar approaches and methodologies. For example, terms such as "networks" and "collaboration" co-appeared in a large number of articles, reinforcing the notion that network analysis is a common approach in the study of interdisciplinarity (4).

as is more specialized and therefore less visible in the broader context of interdisciplinary research.

Proposed analysis: hypotheses on disciplinary integration and potential

- There is substantial potential to integrate less-represented disciplines, such as Physics and Neuroscience, with Social Sciences and Computer Science. For example, the study of human decision-making could benefit from neuroscientific approaches that integrate behavioral data with computational models.
- The growing intersection of technology and health (e.g., telemedicine or digital health) suggests that integrating Computer Science with Medicine and Social Sciences could lead to significant innovations and improved understanding of social dynamics that affect health.
- Collaboration among disciplines can foster the development of new methodologies that integrate data analysis techniques with social theories, which could result in a more robust framework to address complex issues such as climate change, public health, and resource management.

Analyzing the pairs of words with the highest co-occurrence in the interdisciplinary research matrix (4), key conclusions can be drawn about research approaches and underlying dynamics (6).

Figure 6: Top co-occurrences of term pairs in scientific research.

The pair “Social - industry” has the highest co-occurrence (7339), suggesting that research often explores the intersection between Social Sciences and industry. This indicates a focus on how social practices

and theories are applied and affect the business world, suggesting that collaboration between the social sector and industry is fundamental to solving contemporary problems. “Science - methods” and “Science - terms” also show significant co-occurrences, reflecting attention to scientific methodology and its application across disciplines, which is essential for ensuring the validity and applicability of interdisciplinary research.

The frequency of words related to “Management” and “Health” indicates that interdisciplinary research is increasingly linked to effective management and public health. This suggests a focus on how management principles can be applied to improve efficiency in health contexts and how research in these fields can be collaborative and results-oriented. Pairs such as “Social - develop” and “Social - services” show interest in the development of social services and their integration with theory and practice, suggesting that research is oriented toward understanding and improving social infrastructure and well-being. Overall, the strong co-occurrence of terms combining Social Sciences, scientific methods, and applied fields such as management and health suggests that interdisciplinary research is thriving. This approach not only promotes collaboration, but also enables complex problems to be addressed from multiple perspectives.

Less-represented disciplines, such as Molecular Biology or Physics, could benefit from integrating approaches from Social Sciences and management. For example, in biomedical research, one could study how public health policies influence the adoption of new medical technologies, thereby fostering greater integration.

Combining scientific methods with practical applications in industry and management suggests significant innovation potential. Developing collaborations among these disciplines could yield new strategies that address immediate challenges while also promoting sustainable long-term development.

Proposed analysis: hypotheses on relevance and integration

- The interdependence of social terms with management and development approaches suggests research could focus on how scientific innovations impact society, leading to studies on the effectiveness of social programs and public policies.
- Fostering networks among disciplines such as Psychology, Management, and Health could result in more effective research addressing problems like mental health, where social well-being and resource management are critical.

The analysis of the co-occurrence matrix and the

proaches across multiple domains, including health sciences and economics. This reflects recognition that many contemporary problems, such as public health and environmental management, require a deep understanding of social and human factors.

Disciplines such as “Computer” and “Engineering” are also well represented, suggesting growing interest in using technology and engineering to address interdisciplinary problems. This is particularly relevant in contexts where digitalization and technological innovation are increasingly important in research.

To evaluate the influence of different disciplines in interdisciplinary research, a methodology is proposed consisting of summing the rows of the discipline co-occurrence matrix. This technique quantifies the degree of interrelation and influence each discipline exerts over others. The steps and their meaning are described below:

1. Construction of the co-occurrence matrix.

The first stage involves creating a co-occurrence matrix where rows represent different disciplines and columns represent terms related to each discipline. Each cell contains the number of term co-occurrences between the corresponding disciplines. This matrix provides a clear visualization of how disciplines interrelate through shared terms (8).

2. Row sums. Once the matrix is constructed, the values in each row are summed. This sum reflects the total co-occurrences of each discipline with all related terms. This yields a total value indicating how often a discipline interacts with others in the matrix.

3. Interpretation of results. The row-sum results help identify the most influential disciplines in interdisciplinary research. A high value indicates that a discipline has many co-occurrences with other terms, suggesting it is well connected and plays a significant role in interdisciplinary dialogue. By contrast, a low value may indicate that the discipline is less active in interdisciplinary interactions or is approached in a more specialized way (9).

Figure 9: Word cloud based on the frequencies of the selected articles.

Biochemistry (1950): Biochemistry shows the highest number of co-occurrences, indicating its relevance in interdisciplinary research. This may be due to the growing importance of molecular biology and biomedicine, where biochemistry plays a crucial role in understanding biological processes at the molecular level, and its applications in health, agriculture, and pharmacology.

Management (1793): The high co-occurrence in Management suggests significant interest in applying management principles in multiple contexts, from business to social domains. Effective management is fundamental for implementing interdisciplinary solutions and coordinating efforts across diverse knowledge areas.

Agricultural (1786) and Accounting (1759): Both disciplines reflect the importance of practical and analytical approaches in agriculture and accounting. Agriculture is key for sustainable development, while accounting is essential for informed decision-making in business and finance.

Multidisciplinary (1736): This category underscores the integrative nature of current research, indicating that many studies span multiple disciplines, which is fundamental to addressing complex problems.

Disciplines with lower total co-occurrences

Health (1445): Although Health is vital in interdisciplinary research, its lower number of co-occurrences may indicate that studies in this area are often conducted in a more isolated way or that health research is not being connected to other disciplines as strongly as expected.

Environmental (1470): Despite growing attention to environmental problems, its representation in terms of co-occurrences may reflect a more specialized focus that does not necessarily intertwine with other disciplines to the same extent.

Biological (1491): The lower co-occurrence count in Biology could suggest that, although it is a fundamental discipline, it may be approached more specifically, limiting interactions with other fields.

Missing disciplines

The analysis should also consider the absence of some disciplines that could be critical for interdisciplinary research, such as:

Political Science: Integrating this field could enrich research in areas such as public health and social development by addressing how policies influence social well-being.

Education: Education can offer valuable perspectives on learning and knowledge transfer in interdisciplinary contexts, especially in professional training.

Anthropology and Sociology: These disciplines can provide insights into social and cultural dynamics, crucial for understanding how interdisciplinary solutions are implemented and adopted in different contexts.

Examining the term pairs with the highest co-occurrence reveals several combinations that highlight key trends in interdisciplinary research (10):

Science–Social (650): This pair reflects the close relationship between scientific research and social aspects, suggesting that scientific approaches are deeply integrated with the analysis of social phenomena. This link is crucial for addressing contemporary problems requiring both scientific rigor and social sensitivity.

Social–Management (609): The co-occurrence between management and social terms indicates that management is applied not only in business contexts but also in implementing social policies and programs. This highlights the importance of effective management in developing and executing initiatives that affect communities.

Science–Management (408): This combination suggests that science and management are interrelated, especially in applied research where scientific discoveries must be managed and implemented efficiently to be effective in the real world.

Social–Environmental (382): The relationship between social and environmental terms is fundamental, particularly in sustainability contexts. This link indicates a focus on how communities interact with their environment and how resources can be managed responsibly.

Health (376): The high co-occurrence of health-related terms indicates growing concern for public health and social well-being, suggesting that health research is often approached from an interdisciplinary per-

spective that includes social, environmental, and management aspects.

Figure 10: Top co-occurring pairs using disciplines as terms.

References

- [1] Albert-László Barabási. Network science. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 371(1987):20120375, 2013.
- [2] Thomas Gottron and Steffen Staab. *Linked Open Data*, pages 1211–1213. Springer New York, New York, NY, 2018.
- [3] Tom Heath. Linked data: Evolving the web into a global data space. *Morgan & Claypool*, 2011.
- [4] Daniel J Kevles. The national science foundation and the debate over postwar research policy, 1942–1945: A political interpretation of science—the endless frontier. *Isis*, 68(1):5–26, 1977.
- [5] Robert Frodeman. *The Oxford Handbook of Interdisciplinarity*. Oxford University Press, 01 2017.
- [6] Caroline Haythornthwaite. Learning and knowledge networks in interdisciplinary collaborations. *Journal of the American society for information science and technology*, 57(8):1079–1092, 2006.
- [7] Valerie A Haines, Jenny Godley, and Penelope Hawe. Understanding interdisciplinary collaborations as social networks. *American journal of community psychology*, 47(1-2):1–11, 2011.